

ISic1157

I.Sicily inscription 1157

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Chiesa Madre

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140642

1. Θεοῖς Κατ[αχ]-
2. [θ]ονίοις.
3. ΜΗΚΑΛΙ Σουλ-
4. πίκιος Ἄνι-
5. κητος ἔζη-
6. σεν ἔτη ΧΧΧΧ.
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492770

EDCS 39102313

PHI 140642

Bibliography

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